

Experimental

Ethyl bromarylaminoethylene-malonates & -cyanoacetates :

Ethyl bromarylaminoethylene-malonates were prepared by the method of Duffin and Kendall⁴ from the appropriate bromarylamine and ethyl ethoxymethylene-malonate by heating the mixture at 110° and the corresponding cyanoacetates by the method of Snyder and Jones⁵ by heating the mixture of the arylamine, ethyl cyanoacetate and ethyl orthoformate at 160-165° and the acrylates were purified by the usual treatment (details vide Table 1).

3-Carboethoxy- and 3-cyano-4-hydroxybromoquinolines :

Ethyl bromarylaminoethylene-malonate (15 g) or cyanoacetate (10 g) was cyclised to corresponding quinoline in boiling diphenyl ether (150 cc) and the product crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid (Table 2).

4-hydroxybromoquinoline-3-carboxylic acids :

3-Carboethoxyquinolines were hydrolysed by refluxing with 2N ethanolic sodium hydroxide for 3 hours and the 3-cyanoquinolines with an aqueous mixture of sulphuric and acetic acids (each 25 cc). Neutralisation of the basic or acidic solution gave the corresponding carboxylic acids (Table 2) which were purified by repeated alkali and acid treatment. The mixed m.p.s of corresponding acids in both cases did not show any depression.

Elemental analysis of (N) & (Br) were found to be within $\pm 4\%$ of the theoretical value for all the compounds prepared.

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Chromic Acid Oxidation of Some Substituted 2-Hydroxymethylphenethyl Alcohols

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2-Hydroxymethylphenethyl alcohols have been shown¹⁻⁴ to be transformed into their corresponding isochroman-1-ones through the respective isochromans. Substituted 2-Hydroxymethylphenethyl alcohols(I) could now be directly oxidised to isochroman-1-ones(II) with chromic acid in one step following the procedure of Kubota *et al.*⁵. Also, IIf was converted to IIa by catalytic hydrogenation over Pd/C and subsequent treatment with diazomethane.

Ia, R = 4,5-di-OCH₃
 Ib, R = 5,6-di-OCH₃
 Ic, R = 4,6-di-OCH₃
 Id, R = 4,5-O₂CH₃
 Ie, R = 4-CH₃-6-OCH₃
 If, R = 4-C₆H₅-CH₂O-5-OCH₃

IIa, R = 6,7-di-OCH₃
 IIb, R = 5,6-di-OCH₃
 IIc, R = 5,7-di-OCH₃
 IId, R = 6,7-O₂CH₃
 IIe, R = 5-OCH₃-7-CH₃
 IIf, R = 6-OCH₃-7-C₆H₅-CH₂O

Experimental

6,7-Dimethoxyisochroman-1-one : A solution of CrO₃ (0.3 g) in water (0.6 ml) and glacial AcOH (2 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to 2-hydroxymethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenethyl alcohol (I; 0.2 g) dissolved in the same acid (6 ml). The temperature was maintained at 20-22° by occasional external cooling. After stirring for 0.5 hr. at the room temp., it was treated with an equal volume of water, extracted with CHCl₃ (2 × 25 ml), the extract washed with 2N Na₂CO₃, water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. A dark yellow solid left after solvent evaporation was dissolved in dry benzene. It was chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina (30 g) and eluted with the same solvent. An almost colourless solid obtained was crystallised from ethylacetate-pet. ether (b.p. 60-80°) as colourless needles (0.07 g), m.p. 140-141°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of the compound prepared earlier by a different route².

The following compounds were prepared by the method described above and crystallised from ethyl acetate-pet. ether unless otherwise mentioned.

5,6-Dimethoxyisochroman-1-one¹, m.p. 70-71° (37.5% yield) was purified by sublimation (bath temp. 90-95°/0.1 mm) followed by crystallisation from ethyl acetate.

5,7-Dimethoxyisochroman-1-one³, colourless needles, m.p. 97-98° (35% yield).

6,7-Methylenedioxyisochroman-1-one¹, colourless prisms, m.p. 126-27° (25% yield).

5-Methoxy-7-methylisochroman-1-one⁴, cubes, m.p. 79-80° (yield 42% yield).

6-Methoxy-7-benzyloxyisochroman-1-one⁵, yellow shining flakes, m.p. 125-26° on trituration with pet. ether (yield 50%) was debenzylated by catalytic hydrogenation over Pd-C and subsequently treated with diazomethane to furnish 6-methoxy-isochroman-1-one, 139-40°.

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Synthesis of 2, 6-Diaryl-5 : 6-Dihydro-4H-1 : 3-Thiazines

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SEVERAL diversely substituted 2, 6-Diaryl-5 : 6-dihydro-4H-1 : 3-thiazines are synthesized using method of Giordano et al^{1,2}, and their structures confirmed by elemental analysis, infra-red spectra and in few cases mass spectra. These (Table 2) were prepared by condensation of N(Hydroxymethyl)-thiobenzamides³ (Table 1) and styrenes in acetic acid.

Experimental

N-Hydroxymethyl Thiobenzamides: These were prepared by heating a mixture of thiobenzamides (0.02 mole), 200 ml. water, 20 ml. 40% formaldehyde (0.5 mole) on a water bath for 15-30 minutes. Contents were cooled and extracted with ether, ether stripped off after drying to get title products (vide Table 1).

2, 6-Diaryl-5 : 6-Dihydro-4H-1 : 3-Thiazines: To a stirred solution of N-Hydroxymethyl-thiobenzamide (0.045 mole) and styrene (0.045 mole) in glacial acetic acid (70 ml) was added conc. sulfuric acid (0.045 mole) dropwise so as to maintain the reaction mixture around 15°. After addition, stirring at this temperature was maintained for six hours and mixture left overnight at room temperature. It was then poured onto crushed ice and basified with 40% aq. sodium hydroxide keeping temp. ~ 10°. The solution was now extracted with ether, ether

TABLE-1

PHENYL-SUBSTITUTED-N-HYDROXYMETHYL-THIOBENZAMIDES

No.	R	M.P. °C.	% age yield	Molecular Formula	%N		%S	
					Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6	7	8	9
1.	H	65 ^a	91	C ₉ H ₉ NOS	—	—	—	—
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	86	88	C ₉ H ₁₁ NOS	7.64	7.73	17.60	17.67
3.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	84	83	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S	6.99	7.10	16.11	16.24
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	90-91 ^b	87	C ₈ H ₈ ClNOS	—	—	—	—
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	69	84	C ₈ H ₈ BrNOS	5.63	5.69	13.00	13.02
6.	3 : 4-Methylenedioxy.	92	78	C ₉ H ₉ NO ₂ S	6.55	6.63	15.15	15.17

^a. Reported by H. Böhme, and H. H. Hotzel, *Arch. Pharm.* 1967, **300**, 241.

^b. Reported by C. Giordano, *Synthesis*, 1972, No. 1, 34-35.